

1 **Natural flooding events modulate bacterioplankton community structure and**
2 **functional properties in Laguna Chascomús, a hypereutrophic turbid shallow lake.**

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19 **Abstract**

20 Laguna Chascomús, a shallow, eutrophic lake located in the Argentine Pampas, is
21 subject to periodic droughts and floods due to the region's alternating wet and dry cycles.
22 Bacterioplankton communities play a crucial role in the lake's biogeochemical cycles, making
23 it essential to understand the factors influencing their diversity and structure. This study
24 investigates the temporal dynamics of bacterioplankton composition in Laguna Chascomús
25 over a four-year period (2012-2016) through biweekly sampling, during which three significant
26 flood events disrupted normal hydrometric levels. Environmental variables, including
27 temperature, water level, conductivity, and soluble reactive phosphorus (SRP), were
28 monitored, while community composition was assessed using high-throughput sequencing of
29 the 16S rRNA V3-V4 region with Illumina MiSeq. The dominant phyla identified were
30 Cyanobacteria (order *Synechococcales*), Actinobacteriota, and Proteobacteria. Non-metric
31 multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analyses indicated that fluctuations in water level obscure
32 seasonal patterns, with elevated water levels reducing cyanobacterial abundance and
33 promoting Proteobacteria. Under normal conditions, *Synechococcales* dominated, peaking
34 in winter, with Actinobacteriota as the subdominant group. However, during flood events,
35 characterized by lower conductivity and elevated SRP, Actinobacteriota became the dominant
36 phylum, followed by Proteobacteria. In addition, in silico predictions based on the 16S rRNA
37 gene suggest shifts in key metabolic pathways, including carbohydrate metabolism, amino
38 acid metabolism, and the degradation of xenobiotics, particularly agrochemicals. These
39 findings underscore the role of environmental factors, particularly flooding, in driving deviations
40 from seasonal bacterioplankton dynamics. In light of ongoing climate change, these results
41 have important implications for understanding ecosystem functioning and management in
42 shallow lake environments.

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44 **Keywords:** Bacterioplankton, Argentine Pampas, long-term study, community
45 dynamics, seasonal patterns.

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